

A Study of Cardiovascular Manifestations following Venomous Snake Bites in K.R. Hospital MysuruTriveni Shivanagi¹, Ramesh S S², Lavanya B U³¹Postgraduate Department of General Medicine Mysore Medical College and Research Institute²Professor, Department of General Medicine Mysore Medical College and Research Institute³Assistant professor, Department of General Medicine Mysore medical college and Research Institute

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Objectives: Snake bite is a neglected tropical disease. Snake venom is a complex mixture of various enzymes, polypeptides and toxins. Paired fang marks, clinical syndromes, size, shape, pattern of markings, behavior helps to identify poisonous snakes. Snakebite causes local effects at bite site, lymphadenopathy, hematotoxicity, clotting disorders, neurotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, DIC. Cardiac manifestations following snakebite is less stressed complication. Hence the study has been conducted to observe clinical, electrocardiographic and cardiac biochemical changes and to study incidence and pattern of cardiotoxicity.

Methodology: 120 cases admitted to K.R. Hospital, Mysuru meeting the inclusion criteria were considered in 1 year time period between July 2022 to June 2023. It's a single centered, time bound and prospective study. Data was entered into Microsoft excel data sheet and was analyzed using SPSS 22 version software. Categorical data was represented in the form of Frequencies and proportions. Chi-square test was used as test of significance for qualitative data. Continuous data was represented as mean and SD. Independent t test was used as test of significance. ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) was the test of significance to identify the mean difference between more than two groups for quantitative and qualitative data respectively. Paired t test is the test of significance for paired data such as before and after surgery for quantitative and qualitative data respectively. Pearson correlation or Spearman's correlation was done to find the correlation between two quantitative variables and qualitative variables respectively.

Results: The study population was mainly in age group of less than 40 years (78.3%) and 75% people affected are males. People involved in agricultural work (86.7%) are more commonly affected and most common site of bite being right lower limb(76.7%). 78.3% people reached hospital within 12hours. Local signs were present in 90%. Vomiting (27.5%), palpitations (11.7%) were present. 1.7% people experienced hypotension. ECG changes were seen in 42.5%. Elevated troponin I (5.8%) and CKMB in (5%). ECHO was abnormal in (1.6%). ASV was administered to 100%. 1.6% required vasopressor support. 0.8% mortality is observed.

Conclusion: Cardiovascular system involvement following snakebite was not rare, it is mandatory to record ECG and estimation of cardiac enzymes as soon as possible in detecting cardio toxic effects following snakebite.

Keywords: Agricultural work, local signs, vomiting, Palpitation, Snakebite, ECG, 2d ECHO, ASV, Troponin I, CKMB.

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Introduction

Snake bite is a neglected tropical disease. Total 3500 species of snakes, in that about 500 belongs to 4 families of venomous snakes. Commonly encountered poisonous snakes in India are King cobra, Common krait, Russel's viper, Saw scaled viper [1].

An estimated 1.8 to 2.5 million venomous snake bites occur worldwide each year and results in 100000 deaths worldwide [2]. In India snake bites are most common cause of accidental deaths

accounting for 5% of all accidental deaths and 0.5% of all deaths. Total of about 50000 deaths occurs annually [3]. A snake venom contains digestive hydrolases, hyaluronidase, L-amino acid oxidase, phospho mono and diestrases, [5] nucleosidase, DNA ase, NAD-Nucleosidase, phospholipase-A2 and peptidases. Also contain non-enzymatic proteins and polypeptides. Among them hemorrhagins, neurotoxins, cardio toxins are important. [4]

Snake bite is most commonly seen among farmers, herdsman, plantation workers, snake handlers, fisherman, and barefoot walkers. Paired fang marks, clinical syndromes, size, shape, pattern of markings, behavior helps to identify poisonous snakes [5]. Snakebite causes local effects at bite site, lymphadenopathy, hematotoxicity, clotting disorders, neurotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, DIC, cardiac manifestations [6]. Antisnake venom which is effective against four common species is the mainstay of treatment [7]

Cardiotoxicity following venomous snake bites accounts for 36%. Mechanism of cardiotoxicity includes direct toxic effect on the myocardium, coagulation abnormalities, vasospasm induced by hemorrhagins or endothelins (2). Causes of hypotension and shock include hypovolemia, vasodilation, and myocardial dysfunction.

Myocardial infarction following snakebite is due to properties of thrombosis and vasoconstriction by snake venom. Anemia secondary to coagulation alterations and anaphylactic shock [8]. Hence this study is taken up to observe cardiac manifestations in the form of ECG changes and detection of cardiac enzymes. Hence it was mandatory to record ECG and estimate cardiac enzymes as soon as possible in detecting cardiotoxic effects following snakebite. [9]

Objectives

- To observe clinical, electrocardiographic and cardiac biochemical changes following snake envenomation.
- To study incidence and pattern of cardiotoxicity in snake envenomation.

Study Design: Single Centre and Prospective observational study

Study Setting: A Government Tertiary care hospital in Mysuru city.

Study Population: 120

Population Element: Patients presenting with snake bite with signs of envenomation

Sampling Element: Patients presenting with snake bite with signs of envenomation at the study setting.

Study Period: Between July 2022 to June 2023

Sample Size Estimation: The sample size is estimated by population proportion of the snake bite according to the study done by: Anitha M S et al., A prospective study regarding cardiovascular manifestations following snake bite, International Journal of advances in medicine 2017 Feb 4 Vol 4 Issue 1 page 152 which had a prevalence of 36%. Taking 9% as absolute precision and assuming the same prevalence rate in our region also with 95% of confidence interval the sample size is found to be 113. For the convenience purpose, sample size will be rounded off to 120 in our study

Sample size = $4pq/d^2$

Where p = prevalence, q = (1-p) and d = 0.09

Results

A total 120 patients of venomous snakebite and cardiovascular manifestations were analysed according to symptoms, ECG, cardiac enzymes and 2D Echo.

Table 1: Distribution of the Participants in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage	95% CI
18-30 Years	49	40.8%	32.1% - 50.2%
31-40 Years	45	37.5%	29.0% - 46.8%
41-50 Years	17	14.2%	8.7% - 22.0%
51-60 Years	8	6.7%	3.1% - 13.1%
61-70 Years	1	0.8%	0.0% - 5.2%

Figure 1: Distribution of the Participants in Terms of Age

40.8% of the participants were in age group of 18-30 Years. 37.5% of the participants were in age group of 31-40 Years. 14.2% of the participants were in age group of 41-50 Years. 6.7% of the participants were in age group of 51-60 Years. 0.8% of the participants were in age group of 61-70 Years.

Table 2: Distribution of the Participants in Terms of Gender (n = 120)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	95% CI
Male	90	75.0%	66.1% - 82.3%
Female	30	25.0%	17.7% - 33.9%

Figure 2: Distribution of the Participants in Terms of Gender

75.0% of the participants were Male. 25.0% of the participants were Female. Male to Female ratio is 3:1

Table 3: Distribution of the participants in terms of Species Of snake (n = 120)

Species Of Snake	Frequency	Percentage	95% CI
Unknown	73	60.8%	51.5% - 69.5%
Viper	40	33.3%	25.2% - 42.6%
Cobra	5	4.2%	1.5% - 9.9%
Common krait	2	1.7%	0.3% - 6.5%

Figure 3: Distribution of the Participants in Terms of Species of snake

- 60.8% of the participants were not knowing species of snake.
- 33.3% of the participants were bitten by Viper.
- 4.2% of the participants were bitten by Cobra.
- 1.7% of the participants were bitten by Common Krait.

Table 4: Presentation to hospital

Presentation	Yes	No
Vomiting	33 (27.5%)	87 (72.5%)
Palpitation	14 (11.7%)	106 (88.3%)
Restlessness	11 (9.2%)	109 (90.8%)
Chest pain	2 (1.7%)	118 (98.3%)
Syncope	4 (3.3%)	116 (96.7%)
Breathlessness	10 (8.3%)	110 (91.7%)
Neurological manifestations	4 (3.3%)	116 (96.7%)
Bleeding manifestations	5 (4.2%)	115 (95.8%)
Reduced urine output	7 (5.8%)	113 (94.2%)

Figure 4: Distribution of the participants in terms of presentation

- 33(27.5%) of the participants had vomiting.
- 14(11.7%) of the participants had palpitations.
- 11(9.2%) of the participants had restlessness.
- 2(1.7%) of the participants had chest pain.
- 4(3.3%) of the participants had syncope.
- 10(8.3%) of the participants had breathlessness.
- 4(3.3%) of the participants had neurological manifestations
- 5(4.2%) of the participants had bleeding manifestations
- 7(5.8%) of the participants had reduced urine output

Table 5: Distribution of the participants in terms of co-morbidities (n = 120)

Co-morbidities	Frequency	Percentage	95% CI
DM	2	1.7%	0.3% - 6.5%
HTN	1	0.8%	0.0% - 5.2%
None	117	97.5%	92.3% - 99.4%

Figure 5: Distribution of the participants in terms of co-morbidities (n =120)

- 1.7% of the participants had diabetes mellites.
- 0.8% of the participants had systemic hypertension.
- 97.5% of the participants had no co-morbidities.

Table 6: Distribution of the participants in terms of Troponin-I (n = 120)

Troponin-I	Frequency	Percentage	95% CI
Normal	113	94.2%	87.9% - 97.4%
Abnormal	7	5.8%	2.6% - 12.1%

Figure 6: Distribution of the participants in terms of Troponin-I

- 94.2% of the participants had normal Troponin-I.
- 5.8% of the participants had elevated Troponin-I.

Table 7: Distribution of the participants in terms of Ck-Mb (n = 120)

Ck-Mb	Frequency	Percentage	95% CI
Normal	114	95.0%	89.0% - 98.0%
Abnormal	6	5.0%	2.0% - 11.0%

Figure 7: Distribution of the participants in terms of CK-MB

- 95.0% of the participants had Normal Ck-Mb.
- 5.0% of the participants had elevated Ck-Mb.

Table 8: Distribution of the participants in terms of blood pressure (n = 120)

BP	Frequency	Percentage	95% CI
WNL	115	95.8%	90.1% - 98.5%
Hypertension	3	2.5%	0.6% - 7.7%
Hypotension	2	1.7%	0.3% - 6.5%

Figure 8: Distribution of the participants in terms of blood pressure

- 95.8% of the participants had normal bp.
- 2.5% (3) of the participants had hypertension.
- 1.7% (2) of the participants had hypotension.

Table 9: Summary of ECG

ECG	Yes	No
WNL	69 (57.5%)	51 (42.5%)
Atrial flutter	1 (0.8%)	119 (99.2%)
Sinus bradycardia	7 (5.8%)	113 (94.2%)
Sinus tachycardia	40 (33.3%)	80 (66.7%)
ST depression	16 (13.3%)	104 (86.7%)
St elevation	1 (0.8%)	119 (99.2%)
Tall T waves	1 (0.8%)	119 (99.2%)
T-Wave Inversion	8 (6.7%)	112 (93.3%)
Ventricular ectopics	2 (1.7%)	118 (98.3%)

Figure 9: Distribution of the participants in terms of ECG

- 1 (0.8%) of the participants had atrial flutter.
- 7 (5.8%) of the participants had sinus bradycardia.
- 40 (33.3%) of the participants had sinus tachycardia.
- 16 (13.3%) of the participants had ecg ST depression.
- 1 (0.8%) of the participants had ST elevation.
- 1 (0.8%) of the participants had tall T waves.
- 8 (6.7%) of the participants tall T wave inversion.
- 2 (1.7%) of the participants had ventricular ectopics.

Table 10: Distribution of the participants in terms of 2D-Echo (n = 120)

2D-Echo	Frequency	Percentage	95% CI
DCM	1	0.8%	0.0% - 5.2%
IHD	1	0.8%	0.0% - 5.2%
Normal	118	98.3%	93.5% - 99.7%

Figure 10: Distribution of the participants in terms of 2D ECHO

- 1(0.8%) of the participants had DCM.
- 1(0.8%) of the participants had IHD.
- 98.3% of the participants had normal 2D-Echo.

Table 11: Distribution of the participants in terms of ASV Received (n = 120)

ASV Received	Frequency	Percentage	95% CI
Yes	120	100.0%	96.1% - 100.0%

Figure 11: Distribution of the participants in terms of ASV received All of the participants had received ASV

Table 12: Distribution of the participants in terms of Outcome (n = 120)

Outcome	Frequency	Percentage	95% CI
Died	1	0.8%	0.0% - 5.2%
Discharged	119	99.2%	94.8% - 100.0%

Figure 12: Distribution of the participants in terms of outcome 1(0.8%) of the participants died

99.2% of the participants got discharged.

Discussion

The present study is a prospective observational study conducted to determine cardiovascular manifestations following venomous snakebites in K.R. Hospital Mysuru. In present study, among 120 population, the ages of subjects ranged from 19-66 years with mean age being 34.28 ± 9.71 . And median age being 34years .Majority of patients were less than 40 years indicating snakebites are more prevalent in population actively involved in outdoor activities. In a study by Ramakrishna CD et al, Oh Hyun Kim et al, JC menon et al median age of study participants was 40, 57 and 30 years respectively.

In present study, among 120 population, 90 patients (75%) were Males and 30 patients (25%) were females. Male to female ratio being 3:1 indicating Males who are actively involved in outdoor activities are most common culprits of snakebites. In a study by Anitha M S et al, Ramakrishna CD et al, Oh Hyun Kim et al males were 76%, 58%, 70.8% and females were 24%, 42% and 29% respectively of population.

In present study ,among 120 population, 33.3% were bitten by vipers ,4.2% by cobra and 1.7% by krait,60.8% were not able to differentiate species In a study by Ramakrishna CD et al, Subashini Jayawardana et al and Aditya John Binu et al 32.5% 29.5%and 64.7% were bitten by vipers respectively. In present study, among 120 population, Local signs were seen in 90% population. In a study by Anitha M S et al, local signs were seen in all and in a study by

Ramakrishna CD et al, local signs were seen in 93.5% population. Comparison of ECG changes in different studies In present study ,among 120 population, ECG was normal in 57.5% population ,Sinus tachycardia in 33.3%,ST depression in 13.3% , T inversion in 6.7%,Sinus bradycardia in 5.8% , Ventricular ectopics in 1.7% ,Atrial flutter ,Tall T waves and ST elevation in 0.8% cases. In a study by Anitha M S et al, 38% population had Sinus tachycardia, Ramakrishna CD et al, 13.5% population had Sinus tachycardia and Madhusudhan C et al, 44% population had Sinus tachycardia. In a study conducted by Oh Hyun Kim et al, 6.2% had T inversions and Aditya John Binu et al, 37.5% had T inversions. In a study conducted by Sunil kumar et al, 16.7% population had Sinus bradycardia.

In present study, among 120 population, 2D ECHO was normal in 118 (98.3%) patients and 2 (1.6%) patients had abnormal 2d echo in that 1(0.8%) had IHD and 1(0.8%) had DCM. In a study by Ramakrishna CD et al, 1.5% had abnormal 2D echo and in a study by Sunil kumar et al, 4.2% had abnormal 2D echo. Present study is results are comparable with Ramakrishna C D et al.

In present study, among 120 population, 5% patients had elevated CKMB and 5.8% patients had elevated Troponin-I. In a study by Anitha M S et al, 8% patients had elevated CKMB and by Oh Hyun Kim et al, 10.8% patients had elevated Troponin-I. In a study by Madhusudhan C et al, 1.2% patients had elevated CKMB and in a study by Sunil kumar et al, 21.9% patients had elevated Troponin-I In present study, among 120 population, 51.7% patients had hematological complications, 3.3%

neurological, 31% cardiac and 1.7% were in hypotension. In a study by Ramakrishna CD et al, 63.5% had hematological complications and in a study by Oh Hyun Kim et al, 13.3% had cardiac complications in a study by Puneeta Gupta et al, 67.5% had hematological complications and in a study by JC menon et al, 56% had hematological complications and 4.3% cardiac. In present study, among 120 population, 1 patient (0.8%) died in a study by Ramakrishna CD et al, 3% patients died. In a study by Oh Hyun Kim et al, no deaths were seen but in a study by JC menon et al, 3.6% patients died.

Conclusion

In this study even in absence of cardiac symptoms ECG and cardiac enzyme changes detected myocardial damage. Serum enzyme estimation was superior to clinical assessment. Hence it was mandatory to record ECG and estimate cardiac enzymes as soon as possible in detecting cardiotoxic effects following snakebite. Mortality in snakebite envenomation is very less if timely intervened. So snake envenomation is a preventable cause of mortality in tropical countries.

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